

Title: *A Look At Machine Learning Tools in Python SCIKIT-LEARN and SPARK MLIB*

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INTRODUCTION:

SKIKIT-LEARN in Python has a rich set of modules that can be used given different characteristics of the dataset being analyzed. This talk walks through tools available for Machine Learning in Python, and Spark MLIB an attempt is made to understand the comparative features offered by Python, and Spark MLIB machine learning tools so that we can better understand what tool to use for a given problem at hand be it a Big Data problem or problem involving small amount of data. Or some times we have data involving a large number of attributes an extreme case being data having more attributes than number of observations. The data may be discrete or continuous or it may be noisy . Some data may have high correlation between attributes or may have outlier points or may demonstrate heteroscedasticity .Given these differences in the inherent characteristics of a dataset and the need to handle big data we need to understand how to make the best choice of a Machine Learning Tool.

AIM:

The aim of this talk is to understand the most frequently used modules of SKIKIT-LEARN and SPARK MLIB their action and usage. We also try to understand how to integrate the richer functional features of SKIKIT-LEARN with SPARK to take advantage of Parallel Processing and Distributed Processing in Spark with the rich modules of SKIKIT-LEARN.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

In this talk we will go through both supervised and unsupervised learning modules of SKIKIT-LEARN including supervised learning modules for Generalized Linear Models like Ordinary Least Squares, Ridge Regression, Lasso,LARS,LARS LASSO. We will also discuss Stochastic Gradient Decent, Support Vector Machines and Decision Trees. Unsupervised models for clustering like k-Means, Gaussian Mixture Models,co variance estimation, outlier detection and density estimation. For Spark ML Algorithms: common learning algorithms such as classification, regression, clustering, and collaborative filtering. Featurization: feature extraction, transformation, dimensionality reduction, and selection Pipelines: tools for constructing, evaluating, and tuning ML Pipelines. Sample code with snippets using some of these modules will be walked through.

RESULTS:

This talk attempts to achieve an understanding of the choices a Data Scientist has given different characteristics of the datasets and the objective of study and the best modules to use in the circumstance. We will also attempt understand the currently available and future developments to leverage the Parallel and Distributed processing advantages of Spark and the rich functional features of SKIKIT-LEARN.

CONCLUSIONS:

Python and Spark packages for integration of SKKIT-LEARN and Spark use the spark-sklearn package in python to leverage the rich functional features of SKKIT-LEARN and the Distributed processing in Spark. Currently some integration is possible this package contains some tools to integrate the Spark computing framework (<http://spark.apache.org/>) with the popular [scikit-learn machine library](<http://scikit-learn.org/stable/>)

Some actions that are currently possible:

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- train and evaluate multiple scikit-learn models in parallel. It is a distributed analog to the [multicore implementation](<https://pythonhosted.org/joblib/parallel.html>) included by default in [scikit-learn](<http://scikit-learn.org/stable/>)
- convert Spark's Dataframes seamlessly into numpy `ndarray`s or sparse matrices.
- (experimental) distribute Scipy's sparse matrices as a dataset of sparse vectors.

As this is work in progress further development promises more integration.

KEYWORDS:

SKIKIT-LEARN, SPARK MLIB,

BIOGRAPHY:

*Rashmikant Dave completed his **B Sc Chemistry Mathematics from Maharaja Sayajirao University, Vadodara, India and MBA from Sardar Patel University, Vallabhvidyanagar, India.** After his MBA he became interested in the field of Data and Information and for the next 20 years made a career of working in Database Administration Architecture and Development, Enterprise Resource Planning Systems and Analytic s. He worked with **Oracle Corporation in India and US as Principle Database Consultant, IBM in India Sr Manager Database Services and with The City of Hamilton Canada played both the roles of Sr Database Administrator and Data Management Officer at the Building and Licensing Division.** Rashmikant completed the Data Science Specialization with the John Hopkins University Data Science on Coursera.org. He is interested in structured and unstructured databases and designing data pipelines for different end uses he would like to apply new Data Science Tools to Business Areas of Marketing Research, Strategic Management and Financial Analysis.*